

D4.1

Identification of the Nordic ESM community needs for ESM workflows

Report on the use of workflow management systems in the ESM community and the needs for supporting researchers to Open Science.

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Introduction

The Nordic climate modeling community consists of research groups at universities, national meteorological institutes and research institutes, and holds demonstrable world class excellence in the field. Several of these groups contribute to the development of both global and regional climate models (GCMs and RCMs,

respectively) in international projects with collaborations within Europe and the US. However, many users, including PhDs and postdocs, are developing and/or running Earth System Models (ESMs) for more fundamental scientific research and sensitivity studies, and/or cross-disciplinary research (economy & climate, biodiversity, etc.) and they do not always benefit from the advances, technologies or resources leveraged by these large projects/consortiums. One concrete example is IS-ENES project (<https://is.enes.org/>) where only one university, namely Linköpings Universitet (not part of the NICEST2 consortium) from the Nordics is involved; Nordic contributions are mostly from Meteorological services and Research Institutes. From a practical point of view this translates in a lot of time/energy wasted “reinventing the wheel”, repeated simulations, lack of transparency, suboptimal use of the infrastructures, etc. In this context, supporting these researchers and realizing the benefits of Open Science and EOSC are our priorities within NICEST2 and WP4.

Identification of the needs

Methodology

To collect user’s needs, we have asked individual researchers how they used to work with ESMs, and we also collected information from support staff. The methodology used for sampling and collecting inputs is known to be biased towards the NICEST2 partners e.g. very few researchers with no direct links to the NICEST2 consortium provided inputs. Therefore, the different “workflows” and steps we have identified may not fully cover all the current practices but were sufficiently varied in terms of computing & storage resources as well as tooling chain involved to be used as a starting point for the NICEST2 project.

We have identified 7 different types of workflows:

- W1 - Workflow “Running an Earth System Model to simulate specific events/scenarios (for example changing CO₂, or more generally forcings or other model inputs, generating volcanic eruptions, experiment with geoengineering) or for systematic sensitivity studies: running the same source code with different parameters”
- W2 - Workflow “Analyzing and comparing existing simulation outputs (CMIP, etc.)”

- W3 - Workflow “Analyzing and comparing model outputs against observations (co-design)”
- W4 - Workflow “ESM outputs used as input for different models or studies (downscaling, transport modelling/tracking, impacts)”
- W5 - Workflow “Developing an Earth System Model with source modifications, new parameterizations, possible automated testing”
- W6 - Workflow “Running an Earth System Model in an intercomparison framework (well defined protocol)”
- W7 - Workflow “Developing diagnostics and performance metrics tools for routine evaluation of Earth System Models in CMIP”

For each of these workflows, we determined what was needed in terms of:

- Computing resources
- Storage resources
- Acceptable waiting time/expected responsiveness of the system
- Average level of “technical/modelling” expertise of users

We also described the current practices e.g. answering to the following questions:

- Is it run on a “traditional” HPC managed at national level?
- Is the storage accessible from the computing resources without copying back and forth?
- Is it stored on a national storage resource?
- Is a workflow management system (automation) used in the Nordics for executing this workflow? If yes, which one?
- Is a workflow management system used elsewhere for executing this workflow? If yes, which one?
- Is there a specific data management plan and/or template for this workflow?

Current practices & needs

In this section we summarized our findings for each identified workflow and sub-workflow. The detailed workflows and associated information for each sub-workflow are available in Annex-A.

On the level of expertise of end-users

When interviewing researchers and/or discussing their usage of Earth System Models, we found out that very few have a good knowledge of the Earth System Modelling ecosystem (including aspects related parallelization, discretization, optimization, etc.) and how to efficiently run an ESM on a given platform. Most

reported following “recipes” provided by either a more senior scientific staff (usually a postdoc) and/or a support staff and/or online documentation.

Most researchers do not make any code changes but customize their ESM experiments by creating new forcing/inputs, changing parameters in the model, developing custom scenarios, etc. The programs used to make these changes are rarely released or published. If requested by the publisher, a github repository will be created or the code will be dumped in an archive such as zenodo.

However, some researchers make very simple code changes and what we found most surprising is that they usually do not plan to report their changes back to the main repository (this applies in particular to PhD students) even when the code is fully open (such as CESM and/or NorESM): many said that they do not understand the procedure, and/or have not directly contacted the main developers, and/or think that their changes may not be inline with the planned developments. When publishing their research, they usually find it sufficient to describe their code modifications (if that is required by the publisher).

More substantial code changes are made in collaboration with the main developers.

ESMs are used by a wide range of scientists whose main objectives are not necessarily climate modelling. Modellers have an increasing need to work with non-model specialists (for instance field ecologists, economists, social scientists) to improve ESMs and need a framework that can “simplify” the use of Earth System Models. For instance, field ecologists need to be able to set-up new ESM experiments (update forcings/inputs, model parameters, etc.) and compare them with observations.

Other examples given by researchers are studies on the impact of climate changes on the economy, on health related matters, on urbanism, on vegetation and landscape, on agriculture and more generally land use.

These researchers cannot invest as much time as (future) modellers to master the use of ESMs. Several of these researchers would welcome Graphical User Interface for submitting and analyzing their ESM experiments. We would need to take these requirements into consideration when selecting a workflow management system.

On the use/existence of Data Management Plan templates

It is of course not really a surprise but templates for Data Management Plan (DMP) related to Climate Modelling & climate data analysis are not available. Researchers welcome the availability of DMP templates and some have already notified us of the possibility to share their current DMP as a starting point: this information is useful for NICEST2 WP3 (deliverable D3.5). Guidance on where to run and where to store inputs & model outputs or more generally results from their research based on the type of simulations and/or analysis has been requested by a small number of researchers.

More importantly, researchers think that automatically updating their DMPs while running their ESM experiments & analysis would be very useful and they would be more interested in having detailed and accurate DMPs.

On the use of Computing & storage resources

Researchers believe they have no choice when it comes to running ESMs: they prefer to request computing resources on platforms where the corresponding ESM has been scientifically validated. Access to model inputs is also critical (the goal is to avoid having to copy model inputs for each ESM experiment).

Most researchers run on national HPC resources and store model research outputs on national storage resources. In some Nordic countries, there is no need to transfer data from the storage resource to the HPC since there is a shared file system

Researchers who develop ESMs often use their laptop to edit, compile and check their code changes but need to quickly move to an HPC for running any experiments (other than a single column model). Many researchers would welcome the use of cloud computing for their model developments but would like to have an “environment” similar to what they have on their laptop or HPC (which is mostly a terminal where they can run ESMs from the command line).

Most researchers never use containers (docker, singularity, etc.) but would not mind trying it out. However, all the researchers we have contacted believe that the usage of containers will be limited to small use cases (or model development) and were surprised to learn that NorESM can run on HPC-cloud with singularity containers and be as efficient as on [Betzy](#).

Many researchers have expressed an interest in having training and/or hackathons on containers.

On the use of Workflow Management Systems

The main result from our analysis is related to the lack of use of Workflow Management Systems in the Nordics and worldwide. A few large teams/projects in the USA and UK have started to use cylc (<https://cylc.github.io/documentation/>) and/or [Autosubmit](#) but very little is said about the underlying reasons, and it has not been done in the context of Open Science & FAIR research: it is mostly derived from the use of similar workflow management systems by meteorological services, for instance for running their operational forecasts. A more detailed discussion on the pros and cons of some Workflow Management Systems will be given in the next section.

Workflow Management Systems

Introduction to workflow management system

We have selected a subset of Workflow Management Systems, based on current usage within the Earth System Modelling community, the maturity and ease of use for a wide range of users, including scientists that usually do not run Earth System Models but need to analyze and collaborate with Earth System modellers (such as field ecologists, economists, urban planners, etc.). A more comprehensive list of Workflow management Systems is available at <https://github.com/common-workflow-language/common-workflow-language/wiki/Existing-Workflow-systems>.

A few Workflow Management Systems have been considered and evaluated within the climate modelling community for instance within the [IS-ENES2](#) project. Most of these tools were initially developed by the Numerical Weather Prediction community (for instance [ecFlow](#), [Cylc](#)). To our knowledge [Autosubmit](#) is the only Workflow Management System that was directly developed by the climate community. None of these tools considered interoperability with other existing WMS as a requirement, and cross-disciplinary research has not been taken into account.

For NICEST2, and based on the current usage and potential use of Workflow Management Systems, we have considered:

- CWL
- Cylc
- ecFlow
- Autosubmit
- Galaxy
- Snakemake

All the selected WMSs allow describing workflows and tools that makes them portable and scalable from workstations to clusters, cloud, and high performance computing (HPC) environments. Below, you will find a short description of the Workflow Management Systems we considered and for each of them, we answered to the following questions:

- Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?
- Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?
- Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language (CWL) standard?
- Is there a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to compose workflows?
- Does it support running tasks with containers?

Expected added value of using a workflow management system

Automation

Less errors and easier to set up experiments (from blue sky research to CMIP experiments) as well as any ensemble experiments.

FAIR tools and FAIR data

FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (Reproducible).

When selecting a workflow management system, we also aim at supporting the climate community to apply FAIR principles (FAIR tools and data) and ease their move to Open Science.

To get a better overview of what we mean by FAIR computational workflows, we strongly recommend reading the paper “FAIR computational workflows” written by Goble et al., 2019 (DOI: [10.1162/dint_a_00033](https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00033)) and Workflows Community Summit: Advancing the State-of-the-art of Scientific Workflows Management Systems Research and Development, Ferreira da Silva et al., 2021, (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4915801](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915801)).

Sharing and collaboration

Most scientists have shown a strong interest in being able to share their data, software and workflows whenever these are considered “ready for publication”. Therefore, being able to control permissions/access is a must and scientists have requested an easy way to transition from private/shared with their collaborators only (before publication) to fully public data, software and workflows. WorkflowHub (<https://workflowhub.eu/>) is a registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows. We strongly recommend the climate community to upload their workflows in WorkflowHub to increase the FAIRness of their research work.

Required effort for migrating/using workflow management systems

We have explored several existing Workflow Management Systems to identify possible re-use and/or existing expertise within the Nordic countries, in Europe or worldwide; both within the Earth System Modelling community but also outside (in particular with communities that already engage/collaborate with the ESM community). In each case, the objective is also to assess the possible support the Nordic Earth System Modelling Community could get for migrating/using a specific workflow management system.

In relation to NICEST2 work package 3 “FAIR climate data for NorESM and EC-Earth”, we have taken into account the capabilities and/or existing work/tools of the corresponding workflow management system to facilitate the creation of:

- FAIR computational workflows,
- FAIR data and
- FAIR software.

Results on the analyzed workflow management systems

Detailed information about each considered workflow management system and answers to each of the questions can be found in Annex-B. In this section, we summarize our findings.

There is not one workflow management system standing out among the others. Workflow Management Systems are relatively new to the climate community, especially to researchers at Universities. Several of the analysed workflow management systems were very similar: Cylc, ecFlow and to some extent Autosubmit. These three workflow management systems are mostly used/developed by the Numerical Weather Prediction Community and only more recently adopted by the Climate Community. While promising, the community is rather small and no consideration for cross-disciplinary research has been made.

Most workflow management systems are considering the possibility to add metadata for FAIR computational workflows (see FAIR Computational Workflows, Goble et al., 2019, DOI: [10.1162/dint_a_00033](https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00033)) but we found that Galaxy (because it is more than just a workflow management system) has already implemented most of the FAIR workflow principles. In addition, there is already an ongoing collaboration with the Galaxy Community ([EOSC-Nordic](#), [INES](#)). In the next section, we give more details on why we have chosen Galaxy and also why we think this choice will not restrict the Climate Community to a single workflow management system. Indeed, the main objective is first to democratize the use of WMSs within the Climate community and in particular encourage/train researchers to decompose their work into FAIR workflows.

Why Galaxy?

- Galaxy supports a wide range of users from novices (through its web interface) to advanced users (via command line); thanks to its GUI, it would make it possible to teach and expose undergraduate students to Earth System Modelling and more generally introduce the notions of automated workflow and reproducible research.
- Adding a new tool to Galaxy (if it is not already in the [Galaxy Toolshed](#)) is done by making a little Python wrapper and a description in XML where metadata can be easily added to improve the FAIRness of the tools.
- All Galaxy tools already accommodate metadata, including metadata from the [EDAM ontology](#) that can significantly improve the FAIRness of our workflows. The EDAM ontology will be extended for the climate/geosciences community as part of the EOSC-Nordic project. End-users can then use the new tool from the command line or the Galaxy web interface.
- Galaxy is already an EOSC service (listed on the EOSC market place) with free/public access to Galaxy Europe; There is also the possibility to book virtual classroom (dedicated computing & storage resources) for teaching ([Training Infrastructure as a Service](#)); A scientific collaboration within EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Life has been put in place for adopting the [EOSC-Life tool roadmap](#) and following best software practices from the development until the deployment of tools (including containerization of any tools). As a result, we get support (staff) from Galaxy Europe & ELIXIR Europe for our training events & hackathons.
- The Galaxy community is large and there is significant effort to onboard new communities (not only bioinformatics for which Galaxy has been initially developed). For instance, Galaxy Europe supports more than 20 communities with their own subdomain (see <https://galaxyproject.eu/about>).
- Many tools of interest for the Climate community (such as machine learning tools) have been included. Interactive tools such as Jupyter notebooks are also already available.
- Among CWL, Cylc, ecFlow, autosubmit, galaxy and snakemake, Galaxy is the only workflow management system allowing end-users to compose workflows from both the command line and via a graphical user interface (see [Galaxy tutorial on creating, editing and importing galaxy workflows](#)). This GUI makes it easier to clearly see dependencies and provides guidance while the workflow is being composed and later published (with also check lists for improving FAIRness, etc.). Galaxy is also working on supporting CWL standard: [galaxy2cwl](#) is a lightweight tool to convert Galaxy workflow files to abstract CWL.
- Galaxy is “coarse-grained” and also includes the notion of “workflows of workflows” e.g. a workflow can become a new “Galaxy tool”: for the climate community, it means that an ESM workflow (for instance written with Cylc

and/or CWL) could be added as a new tool to Galaxy (and therefore be used both from the command line and via a graphical user interface).

Roadmap for NICEST2 Task 4.1

We plan to leverage the existing collaboration between EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Life for Tool roadmap (packaging, containerization, etc.) to implement tools and workflows as identified in Annex-A.

When it comes to data management, we will explore different solutions in collaboration with EOSC-Nordic. The need to streamline data movement (and overall to reduce data copies as much as possible) has been clearly identified (it is currently one major bottleneck for researchers and it definitely hinders their ability to smoothly move to cloud computing, including HPC-cloud). As part of EOSC-Nordic, we have already tested different solutions, for instance converting netCDF model outputs to data formats that are more efficient on cloud resources ([zarr](#), [caterva](#); zarr is compatible with [xarray](#) so it would not significantly change researchers' day to day habits), creating online catalog with [intake](#) or [SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs](#) and finally offering remote access (public or private) with s3 and/or s3-compatible object storage (such as [minio](#)).

One major task, in several of the identified workflows, is to run an Earth System Model: [CESM](#), the community Earth System Model developed and maintained by NCAR is already available in Galaxy and NorESM could also be added (a conda package and corresponding container are already available). Below is an example of Galaxy workflow (see Figure-1):

Figure-1: Workflow for running a CESM B1850 f18_g17 experiment on Galaxy. This example workflow sets-up the case, compiles the code, runs one month and generates plots (surface temperature).

While Galaxy is highly configurable and flexible on how to run tools e.g. Galaxy can use different back-end and queuing systems, we have made all our tests on Galaxy Europe where Galaxy tools are run either as conda packages (from conda-forge and/or bioconda) and/or within containers (docker, singularity).

To introduce CESM in Galaxy Europe we have:

- Packaged CESM in bioconda
- Generated automatically containers
- Created an XML wrapper with metadata (EDAM ontology and Galaxy metadata) so that CESM Galaxy tool can be called from the Galaxy Graphical Interface, command line (from any terminal) or JupyterLab (for instance the Galaxy Climate JupyterLab).

Then whenever a user creates a workflow (or runs the CESM Galaxy tool), he/she can:

- Share his/her history either with everyone or only with his/her collaborators (end-users have full control on permissions/access to data and histories);
- Reference/add his/her Galaxy history to Rohub (<https://www.rohub.org/>) as a Research Object (public or private);
- Publish his/her workflow in Workflow Hub (<https://workflowhub.eu/>) as a FAIR workflow.

EC-EARTH is not open source which makes it more difficult to be included in Galaxy. However, EC-EARTH containers (registered in private repositories) will be developed and tested within NICEST2. As a consequence, all workflows in Annex-A where an ESM needs to be run will be demonstrated with NorESM and/or CESM. For any other workflows, we will make use of both NorESM and EC-EARTH model outputs (or more generally any model outputs publicly available from either researchers' simulations or CMIP6).

Conclusion

In this deliverable, we have made an attempt at identifying the needs of the climate community when it comes to Workflow Management Systems. During the NICEST2 project, we will be using Galaxy but make sure that our developed workflows can interoperate with other WMSs (at least as sub-workflows). During the second part of the NICEST2 project, we will implement the workflows we have identified as key for the climate community (see Annex-A) and will work in collaboration with WP3 to ensure the FAIRness of our tools, data and workflows.

In addition, and as a way to prepare for Open Science & FAIR research, we strongly recommend the climate community to:

- Organize regular outreach and onboarding events (training/hackathon/videos) to disseminate the findings and recommendations to the Nordic communities;
- Disseminate information on available training on programming and best software practices (The Carpentries, CodeRefinery, PRACE, etc.);
- Share their “recipes” on how to efficiently run an ESM on a given platform (optimization options, processor layout, file system hints, etc.) so that other scientists can benefit from it;
- Create an account on <https://usegalaxy.eu/>, look at the available tutorials and begin to familiarize themselves with the tool shed;
- Create an account on RoHub (<https://www.rohub.org/>) to see what [Research Objects](#) can bring for their research lifecycle management, to find informations and other relevant pieces of work, and to expand their interactions both within their community and outside;
- Upload their workflows in WorkflowHub e.g. <https://workflowhub.eu/> to increase the FAIRness of their research work and make it more visible in their own community and beyond;
- Report their code changes back to the main repository or at least to the ESM code developers (even if they do not incorporate these directly into the next release, they would get a better pictures of what required modifications and/or can be improved);
- Seriously think about a Data Management Plan which has to be considered as a “live” document and needs updating throughout research work advances;
- Seek advice regarding the most suited platform to do their ESM related work (whether it relates to teaching/training, testing, development, small run, large experiments, etc.) and do not hesitate to try various options since a HPC is not necessarily the most sensible choice;
- Also investigate alternative storage possibilities, in particular for the long term archiving;
- Consider exploiting containers to run ESMs as they come at no cost in terms of performance and provide a well-defined software environment which they

will be able to retrieve on many different platforms, from laptop to cloud and HPC;

- Whenever possible decompose their tasks (data pre-processing, simulations, data extraction, data post-processing, plots, etc.) in “chunks” which can then be made into workflows (or sub-workflows) and reused by their future selves or others;
- Use a Workflow Management System, starting with simple cases (to get a feel about how that works) and progressively increasing complexity, especially for sequences that require a lot of manual interventions and are potential source of errors (data inside a workflow is never mistaken and follows the pre-defined path).

Annex-A

Workflows

W1	Running an Earth System Model to simulate specific events/scenarios or for systematic sensitivity studies	
Description	<p>End users will exploit one Earth System Model using the same source code but changing different parameters. The ESM is often run in ensemble mode. A control (possibly also run in ensemble mode) is required to later compare the results and calculate anomalies.</p> <p>This workflow is typically used for changing CO₂ (abrupt x4, for example) or more generally forcings (or characteristics of emissions) or other model inputs, simulating eruptions (injection of various types of volcanic aerosols, with different concentrations, durations, heights, etc.), experimenting with geoengineering, or for systematic sensitivity studies where a single parameter is changed (many different values).</p>	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW1	<p>Prepare and Run a control experiment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Base code is used from fully validated ESM (configuration is scientifically and technically validated on the target platform). • Usually performed many times by different researchers from different groups because it is hard to find published control experiments. • Whenever published, data may miss important information about the setup (including processor layout, target platform, options, etc.) and published control experiments may not be re-usable.
2	SW2	<p>Quickly analyze the ESM control experiment (to make sure everything ran correctly):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually done at the very end e.g. after spending a lot of CPU hours. • Researchers only focus on components and variables they are familiar with, and may miss important problems (i.e., looking at outputs from the atmospheric component when a “problem” originates from the ocean, etc.). • Sometimes this step is skipped because researchers blindly trust the ESM, whereas obviously the core developers have not tested everything.
3	SW3	Prepare inputs for running a customized experiment:

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers develop their own codes for customizing their experiments but never share their programs (and not even the resulting data/forcing, etc.).
4	SW1	Prepare and Run a “customized” experiment.
5	SW2	Quickly check customized experiments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers usually check after the end of the simulation and not as soon as data is available.
6	SW4	Compare two experiments from the same ESM and same configuration (components, resolution, machine, etc.): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually each researcher develops his own programs from scratch. Very little is shared (many researchers consider that this step is part of the “learning” process and others have to go through it also). • Programs developed/used are often not shared and not re-used/reproducible.
7	SW5	Publish Control experiment e.g. archive it in a public repository: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No standard procedure e.g. ad-hoc metadata (if any; except those required to publish the related paper in a journal). • The goal is not to be re-used but to make data public as required by publishers.
8	SW5	Publish/archive a “customized” experiment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually performed together with step 7.

W2	Analyzing and comparing existing simulation outputs (CMIP, sensitivity studies, scenarios/events, etc.)	
Description	This workflow is used after W1 or W6. It requires all model outputs to be on the same grid and temporal resolutions. It may also involve a post-processing stage to “CMORize” the data in conformance with particular conventions or standards.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW6	CMORization or similar: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This step is not always necessary when comparing with the same ESM or if the two ESMs have computed the same “variables” (or have a subset of common variables that will be used for the

		<p>analysis).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This may be an “ad-hoc” CMORization if the variables of interest are not those used in CMIPs.
2	SW7	<p>Regridding (horizontal and/or vertical):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This step may not be necessary if the comparison is done between the same ESM (different experiment) or if the two models have “similar” grids.
3	SW4	<p>Compare model experiments (after regridding, vertical interpolation & CMORization or similar).</p>
4	SW8	<p>Publish results from ESM analysis. Very similar to SW5 but here we do not publish ESM model outputs but post-processed ESMs (means, anomalies, etc.) and plots/figures (with only the data used for plotting).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usually very ad-hoc workflow. Can be published as part of additional data in the paper publication process; rarely published to be re-used/reproduced. Code used for generating plots/analysis data is not always published “properly” e.g. following FAIR principles (FAIR data and FAIR software).

W3	Analyzing and comparing model outputs against observations (co-design)	
Description	This workflow is used for instance before W5 or as a standalone study. In addition to selecting an area of interest and sometimes interpolating model outputs to observation locations, end users often need to derive new parameters either from the model outputs or from observations so that they can be compared. This workflow can be executed either by modellers or by “observers”.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW9	Select area or location of interest from existing ESM model outputs (previous simulation, CMIP, etc.) with possibly time-interpolation/rescaling (mean, etc.).
2	SW10	Extract/fetch observations to prepare them for comparisons. This step may include some bias corrections.
3	SW11	<p>Compare model results with observations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usually very ad-hoc plots when done within a research context.
4	SW8	Publish ESM vs observation analysis/visualization

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only when mandatory (as part of a publication) and not following any FAIR principles (but mostly following publisher's guidelines if any).
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W4	ESM outputs used as input for different models or studies (downscaling, transport modelling/tracking, impacts)	
Description	This workflow requires re-formatting/regridding model outputs to specific format/grid and/or time range. It is specific to the ESM and model used for the study. Therefore, it is possible to provide a general framework but the actual workflow would need to be adapted for each use case.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW7	Regridding (time & space): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> May not be a separate step and performed together with Step-2.
2	SW12	Reformat data to prepare it for the model to be used <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sometimes the program to regrid and reformat data is provided by the model to be used (for instance WRF has a Preprocessing System called WPS) If not provided, researchers develop ad-hoc programs that are usually not shared and not meant to be reused.
3	SW13	Run a new model (regional/transport, etc.) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steps required for running this model are usually very similar to an ESM (prepare, run, post-process/visualize, publish data).
4	SW16	Publish model results: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usually very little information regarding the provenance of the input data is provided, only the file name (and there is no way to find out if a particular file has been modified).

W5	Developing an Earth System Model with source modifications, new parameterizations	
Description	This workflow is used to test source code changes (such as new	

	parameterizations, introduction of new physical processes, bug fixes, etc.). Ideally, the source code changes are first tested locally by the end users, then the modified code undergoes automated testing when pushed to github/gitlab (or similar). Finally the scientific validity has to be verified, and there will often be several iterations until the approved changes become an integral part of a new release.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW14	Make a source code change to an ESM, compile and test it (very short run, sometimes only a few time steps or days).
2	SW1	Make a “control” experiment.
3	SW1	Make a “customized” experiment to test the code changes from a scientific point of view (duration may vary depending on the code changes).
4	SW2	Quickly check control experiment.
5	SW2	Quickly check customized experiments.
6	SW11	Compare the model with observations (for instance when running a single column model). This step may be skipped by researchers who only perform model development from a “theoretical” point of view (and only evaluate how the models “behaves” against the theory, without necessarily any reference measurements).
7	SW17	Feedback results to “observers” (or field experimentalists) for instance to define new/different measurement campaigns (i.e., to better specify which quantities should be measured and how).
8	SW4	Compare two experiments (control & customized with code changes).
9	SW14	May start again from step-1 to improve the code changes using feedback from modellers and observers.
10	SW15	Publish ESM code changes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be a very long process so the researcher may simply make a copy of the original code and add his/her changes in a separate repository. • The changes may never be added to the main code (depending on the type of change, on the ESM, and on the core developers’ policy in this matter).
11	SW5	Publish Control experiment e.g. archive it in a public repository.
12	SW6	Publish customized experiment (with code changes) e.g. archive it in a public repository: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually no link with code changes.

13	SW8	Publish ESM vs. observation analysis/visualization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only if required by the publisher.
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W6	Running an Earth system model in a model intercomparison framework (well defined protocol)	
Description	This workflow is usually developed by a modeller who has a very good overview of the protocol to be followed (for instance within CMIP6). The role of the person running the workflow is to monitor and make sure everything is running seamlessly (i.e., that the model does not crash and, should that happen, fix the problem then resubmit, that none of the files produced are “lost” during the transfer or archiving processes, etc.). Most of the time, simulations are performed in ensemble mode and a post-processing (such as CMORization) is included to prepare model outputs for ESGF publication. ESGF publication is also included after all the quality checks have passed.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW3	Prepare inputs for running a CMIP-like experiment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follows a very well defined protocol or some inputs may already exist (scripts/codes used to generate the input files for the purpose of the experiment are not usually publicly available and the whole process is not always transparent).
2	SW1	Prepare and run the experiments.
3	SW2	Quickly check experiment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually done after running quite a lot while it could be done more regularly to spot any problems early.
4	SW18	Scientific validation of the experiment. Usually not an in-depth analysis of the data before publication (this is why data may be retracted afterwards and updated).
5	SW6	CMORization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very often the CMORization is not done by the person who ran the simulation, it requires a lot of manual interventions which are potentially a source of errors. Some modelling groups accumulate all the simulations outputs for a “CMORization person” to transfer and convert after the end of the runs.
6	SW19	Publication to ESGF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follows a strict protocol; the person who is in charge of publishing data to ESGF is usually not the one who ran the simulations.

W7	Developing diagnostics and performance metrics tools for routine evaluation of Earth system models in CMIP	
Description	In this workflow, the end-user will modify and/or further develop existing diagnostic tools (using for instance ESMValTool or other ESM diagnostic packages). ESM outputs are already CMORized.	
Step id	Sub-workflow	Sub-workflow description
1	SW20	<p>Collect needs from scientists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For large projects such as CMIPs, diagnostic tools are usually developed by dedicated staff. • Often use a framework that they already know without trying to find out if the diagnostic has already been developed by others or if new “tools” exist, or how it will be maintained.
2	SW21	<p>Code changes/new diagnostic and test it (not necessarily from a scientific point of view but to make sure that at least it does not fail). For development, it may be run/developed with a sample dataset rather than CMIP/large dataset.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control should be used to keep track of code changes (not always the case e.g. researcher may only push/deposit changes at the very end of the process). • Automatic testing could be put in place to facilitate code development.
3	SW22	<p>Scientific validation of the newly developed diagnostic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May require copying large datasets to the post-processing platform, especially if the diagnostic tool cannot open/manipulate remote files. • May be done by another person.
4	SW23	<p>Publish/release new diagnostics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not be part of a specific publication (software publication is not very much used yet in the climate community). • May not be reported/merged to a larger/main base code (for instance ESMValTool). • May not follow best software practices (both for development and deployment).

Description of sub-workflows

For this deliverable, we do not detail each sub-workflow but provide information on the computing & storage resources and where it is usually run, by who (novice, competent practitioner, etc.) and whether a workflow management system is used, etc.

SW ID	SW description & Information on available/used resources
SW1	<p>Prepare and run an ESM experiment:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC (national)</i> Store data on: <i>disk directly on the HPC</i> Level of expertise required: <i>advanced. So often experiments are prepared by skilled staff and handed over to researchers (prone to errors and may have to wait for technical staff to support scientists).</i> Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>need a very responsive system for creating the experiment (set-up, compilation, etc.) but not for running the ESM experiment (researchers can wait quite a long time for their experiment to start and to finish).</i> Data transfer: <i>from HPC to National Research Data storage resources (NIRD project area, Swestore, Allas).</i> Workflow Management System: <i>Not used in the Nordics. Cylc is sometimes used by some international teams but not well established; the goal is not to be FAIR.</i> Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. Everyone writes their own and may not follow best practices.</i></p>
SW2	<p>Quickly check experiment:</p> <p>Run on: <i>Sometimes on HPC (same as for running ESM) to avoid transfer of data. Most of the time on post-processing nodes/cloud computing resources.</i> Store data on: <i>disk often in temporary folders as the data and/or plots produced are not meant to be kept or published.</i> Level of expertise required: <i>intermediate (may require some programming experience; at least to open/plot data).</i> Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>yes. Usually interactive work (no queuing system and X Window System expected)</i> Data transfer: <i>No</i> Workflow Management System: <i>No</i> Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. data/plots are not kept.</i></p>
SW3	<p>Prepare input data for running with an ESM:</p> <p>Run on: <i>usually on the same HPC where the ESM is to be run. However, it could be run anywhere if input data, etc. are available.</i></p>

	<p><i>Preferably run on a system with no queuing time; where researchers can make use of interactive tools (such as Jupyter notebooks). Need to visualize and may require several iterations/versions before researchers are “satisfied” so cloud computing is more appropriate than HPC or HPC-cloud.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>HPC</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>Intermediate (programming expertise is required and many researchers struggle because of a lack of knowledge).</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>yes. Usually interactive work (no queuing system and X Window System expected); at least for developing the algorithm/program.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>A copy may be kept on more “permanent” storage such as NIRD project area, Swestore or Allas.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. This step is usually not taken into account when submitting a DMP. No versioning of the data and no persistent identifier. No “link” between a custom experiment and its corresponding input data. Customized input data may be publicly available (even when associated with a scientific paper).</i></p>
SW4	<p>Compare two experiments from the same ESM and same configuration (components, resolution, machine, etc.):</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform such as NIRD toolkit. Could be run on any cloud computing platform (no need for HPC or HPC cloud). May require GPUs for visualization and processing (could significantly speed-up analysis & visualization).</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>disk on semi-permanent storage such as NIRD project area, Swestore or Allas.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>Intermediate to advanced. Very often customized programs are used and the quality of the resulting analysis and visualizations greatly vary from one researcher to another. There are no standard procedures and ad-hoc programs are rarely published and shared. No best software practices followed.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>for large experiments, users are expected to submit a batch job to process all their data. However, researchers have asked to be able to use a more responsive system/platform; possibly with GPUs to speed-up analysis; but at least with lots of memory. Interactive usage with Jupyter notebooks (and dask for parallelism) is often requested by researchers.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>No. Everything is done on the same post-processing platform where data is usually accessible without copying it.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Very ad-hoc and interactive step.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. Data produced as part of</i></p>

	<p>the analysis are stored as is, with very few or no metadata (except those kept in netCDF files; metadata may be wrong; not checked). Programs used for creating this data and plots are usually not shared and when published there is no “link” between the data and the software used to generate it. No persistent identifiers are generated during this process.</p>
SW5	<p>Publish an ESM experiment e.g. archive it in a public repository:</p> <p>Run on: <i>any platform where data to be published is accessible (cloud computing, post-processing platform, etc.). No need to use HPC or HPC-cloud.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>public archive/repository. When available researchers use their national data archive service. Otherwise Pangea, zenodo (if not too big) and any other public repositories.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>novice</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>researchers are expected to be able to quickly submit an “archive” request but do not mind to wait quite a lot of time before that is completed. They have asked to be able to make this request through a command line API and not having to switch from a GUI for instance to add additional metadata (NIRD archive).</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>Yes. From storage to Archive.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Sometimes but not really. What is missing is clear information on metadata required for making the published data FAIR. This metadata should be collected during the experiment (and not created at the end) to make sure published experiments can be found and reused.</i></p>
SW6	<p>CMORization or similar e.g. compute new variables, change units, interpolate on pressure levels, etc.:</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform where data is accessible. It could be run anywhere e.g. from any cloud services provided data is accessible.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>usually same storage resources as non-CMORized data.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>advanced. Only a few people really know how to CMORize ESM data.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>intermediate. Habitually uses a batch queuing system. Mostly I/Os. Researchers do not expect to get results very quickly; especially when processing large experiments. However, sometimes, when a deadline approaches, this has to be done in an emergency.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>No.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Even though there is often some kind of procedure in place because the person who runs the CMORization is not the person who ran the simulation.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. And at the end both raw</i></p>

	and CMORized data are kept on disks.
SW7	<p>Regridding (time & space):</p> <p>Run on: <i>Very often on HPC because post-processing resources are too limited (not enough memory and/or CPUs). This SW could be run on any cloud computing resources (no need for HPC or HPC-cloud). It can be very time consuming and cumbersome task.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>if run on cloud or any processing platforms, data may need to be transferred if the next step is run on HPC.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: advanced. Most researchers do not regrid data and know very little about regridding.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>for testing and setting up the system must be very responsive (no waiting time; interactive work). For regridding large amounts of data (production), researchers usually submit jobs or wait for quite a while before getting all their data regridded.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>Most of the time, it is not necessary.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: No</p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): No.</p>
SW8	<p>Publish results from ESM analysis e.g. post-processed model outputs such as means, anomalies, etc. and plots/figures (with data used for plotting):</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform with direct access to data. Could be run on any cloud resources provided the data is accessible.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>disk storage such as NIRD project area, SWestore or Allas.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: novice. Anyone should be capable of publishing data they have produced. In practice, whatever is published is usually lacking metadata information that would make it FAIR.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>Researchers do not want to wait to publish their results; at least to initiate the process of publication. They particularly like zenodo where the publication process is fast and efficient.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>From data storage to archive/public repository.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: No. <i>Very ad-hoc procedure.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): Partially. Often forgotten when writing DMPs (or very vague). There is no “standard” procedure so publication can differ from one researcher to another (and even from one experiment to another).</p>

SW9	<p>Select area or location of interest from existing ESM model outputs with possibly time-interpolation/rescaling (mean, etc.) for future comparisons with for instance observations:</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform. Any cloud computing resource with access to data would be suitable.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>disk; usually on private project area. Intermediate data is often not kept.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>novice.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>usually run as an interactive task (jupyter notebook). Low tolerance to waiting time even with large amounts of data to be processed. It is therefore important to store data to speed-up time series access.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>No. Sometimes data is streamed. Usually stored locally and/or in memory.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. At best a jupyter notebook or a script.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Never part of a DMP. Mostly intermediate data.</i></p>
SW10	<p>Retrieve observations, select area/location (for instance when using satellite or global/regional gridded observation) and apply some bias-corrections:</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform or any cloud resources.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally and/or in-memory for further processing.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>novice (need basic programming experience). However a higher level of expertise may be required depending on the observations (some are stored in complex data format).</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. No batch queue system expected.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>From data provider (where observations are stored) to local storage.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Scripts are often shared as examples on how to retrieve the corresponding type of observations.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Data providers are usually mentioned in the DMP; however data size is often difficult to estimate and not reported once downloaded.</i></p>
SW11	<p>Compare model results with observations e.g. plot time series:</p> <p>Run on: <i>post-processing platform or any cloud computing with access to the data.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>could be anywhere if accessible (such as minio or s3-compatible storage).</i></p>

	<p>Level of expertise required: intermediate. Programming experience usually required; researchers often struggle to adopt a good strategy (to avoid loading too much data in memory, etc.)</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>usually interactive workflow so do not expect queuing time, except when run routinely as part of large experiments.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>data could be streamed. Usually run on a platform with direct access to storage. Results stay on the same platform.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. sometimes a script or jupyter notebook. Often not shared.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>No. Plots and derived products are usually not mentioned in the DMP.</i></p>
SW12	<p>Reformat data to prepare it for the model to be used. WRF Preprocessing System is an example:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC where the model will run. Could be run on HPC-cloud.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>HPC</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: novice to intermediate, depending on the model (for instance WRF is quite simple because it already has a WRF Preprocessing System which is well documented; other models can be seen as more difficult).</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>usually run as an interactive task even with a large number of input files to process.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>ESM data that will be prepared to be used as inputs need to be transferred from an archive or at least storage project area (NIRD project area, Swestore or Allas) if data is not accessible from HPC.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Even though steps are very well defined, users need to execute them manually.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Usually mentioned in the DMP. However, the resulting data (used as input to the model) are considered as intermediate data and not always kept.</i></p>
SW13	<p>Run a model (regional/transport, etc.) that uses ESM outputs as inputs:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC even though HPC-cloud or cloud computing could be used.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally on the HPC or cloud storage.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: novice to advanced depending on the model to be run.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>same as for running an ESM e.g. users usually expect to submit a batch job and can wait.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>No except if model inputs are not available on the compute platform yet.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No but some models use very complex scripts and sometimes cylc.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Data generated is usually</i></p>

	mentioned in the DMP.
SW14	<p>Make a source code change to an ESM, compile and test it (short run):</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC while it could be run on any cloud computing resources or HPC-cloud. Performance is not necessary but may require a sufficient number of CPUs for testing. This is an area where containers would bring considerable benefits (having the same compilers and software environment should ensure consistent model behavior).</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally. Data is not expected to be kept for long.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: advanced. Only a few researchers make code changes to an ESM. Do not always follow best software practices (especially at PhDs level so their code changes may be “lost”).</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Users do not expect to wait but usually have to when on HPC (queues). Would greatly benefit from using cloud computing (or HPC-cloud).</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>sometimes for input data. Outputs are usually analysed locally and then removed.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Very manual process.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): Not mentioned. Data is not kept.</p>
SW15	<p>Publish ESM code changes:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC if tests on HPC. Could be done anywhere (from the computing resources used for testing).</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally and on a repository such as github or gitlab</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: intermediate (requires knowledge of a version control system and best software practices).</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Do not expect to wait.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>local to remote repository (github/gitlab).</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Very manual work.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): Software changes are not often mentioned in the DMP.</p>
SW16	<p>Publish results from regional/downscaling simulations:</p> <p>For instance model outputs from WRF or any other regional model, transport model such as FLEXPART, etc. Information on the ESM data used as inputs is not always well reported:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC or any platforms used to run the model simulations.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>public repository/archive such as pangea, NIRD archive.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: novice.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>do not want to wait to initiate transfer/publication.</i></p>

	<p>Data transfer: <i>from local storage to archive.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Always very manual while this task could be automated with creation of all the necessary metadata.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>usually mentioned in the DMP but data size is not mentioned (not known when writing the DMP and never updated).</i></p>
SW17	<p>Feedback results to “observers” (or field experimentalists) for instance to define new/different measurement campaigns.</p> <p>Usually as a report with plots and possibly data that can be easily manipulated by non-modeller specialists:</p> <p>Run on: <i>laptop and/or shared document such as google or hackMD.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>not very secure and long-term.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>novice.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Researchers expect to access this resource immediately.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>sometimes info is sent by email.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Never documented and not taken into account in the DMP. Often information is not published and may be lost.</i></p>
SW18	<p>Scientific validation of an ESM experiment:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC. Could be run on any cloud computing resources with access to ESM experiment results.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally and then transfer to storage such as NIRD project area, Swestore or Allas.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>intermediate. Very often used existing packages that create lots of plots and the study is completed with customized analysis/plots.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>many researchers are used to submit batch jobs for this task. It can take quite a while when the experiment to analyse is long.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>Not always. Sometimes data is still available on HPC. Often need to transfer data from storage (NIRD project area, Swestore or Allas) to HPC if data is not directly accessible.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No but scripts/tools are usually available (at least for the standard validation). Customized scripts, programs are not always shared.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Often mentioned because plots are published “online”.</i></p>
SW19	<p>Publish ESM outputs to ESGF (after CMORization):</p> <p>Run on: <i>usually on post-processing platform or on HPC</i></p>

	<p><i>(depending on where the data is).</i></p> <p>Store data on: ESGF node (usually on a national storage resource in the Nordics)</p> <p>Level of expertise required: high. Only a few people know how to publish to ESGF. It requires special “permissions” so not everyone can publish to ESGF.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>researchers do not expect this step to be interactive. They can wait for quite a long time before having their data published and it is not a problem.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>from storage to ESGF node if necessary.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No but scripts are usually available (but not necessarily shared).</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): Yes. Usually very clear and detailed information as researchers follow a well established protocol.</p>
SW20	<p>Collect needs from scientists for developing new diagnostics.</p> <p>Reports, questionnaire, plots showing mock-up diagnostics, etc.:</p> <p>Run on: <i>google forms or any university/institutional questionnaire “system”</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>varies but usually on institution premises.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: novice.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Do not expect to wait to collect results and analyze results.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>often not.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. If a program is developed to analyse the results, it is usually not shared and often not kept in a repository (github/gitlab).</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): Rarely mentioned in the climate science community (not really considered as “data”).</p>
SW21	<p>Develop/update diagnostics and test it (not from a scientific point of view but to make sure that at least it does not fail):</p> <p>Run on: <i>laptop, post-processing platform. Could be run on any cloud computing resources (no need for HPC or HPC-cloud).</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally (data is not meant to be kept and code changes are expected to be versioned with a proper version control system such as git).</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: advanced. Only very few scientists develop new diagnostics.</p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Do not expect to wait; very interactive.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>Should not be necessary except for testing e.g. test data sets are usually required.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>This development phase is never mentioned in the DMP.</i></p>

SW22	<p>Scientific validation of an ESM diagnostic:</p> <p>Run on: <i>HPC or post-processing platform (e.g. where data is available).</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>locally. Data is not necessarily kept once the validation is finished.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>intermediate. Mostly require scientific expertise. Data/plots may be generated and made available to the scientists who will make the validation.</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>medium. With a large dataset, it can take some time to run (sometimes a batch system is used). Generation of plots/data products could easily be automated.</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>usually the code is transferred/copied where data is available.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No. Some scripts may be available.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>partially mentioned (if data is meant to be kept). Storage necessary to run the diagnostics (intermediate files) is not assessed (or even known).</i></p>
SW23	<p>Publish/release new diagnostics (tool):</p> <p>Run on: <i>laptop or cloud computing resource.</i></p> <p>Store data on: <i>on a repository such as github/gitlab.</i></p> <p>Level of expertise required: <i>intermediate (requires knowledge of version control system).</i></p> <p>Required responsiveness/expected waiting time: <i>high. Do not expect to wait at least for pushing changes (but may have to wait for their PR to be merged).</i></p> <p>Data transfer: <i>from local storage to remote & public repository.</i></p> <p>Workflow Management System: <i>No but not really necessary.</i></p> <p>Data Management Plan (template): <i>Never mentioned.</i></p>

Annex-B

CWL

CWL stands for Common Workflow Language and is an open standard following the [Open-Stand.org principles for collaborative open standards development](#). CWL is developed by a multi-vendor working group consisting of organizations and individuals aiming to enable scientists to share data analysis workflows. Anyone can contribute.

More information is available at <https://www.commonwl.org/>.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

CWL has been used within the DARE H2020 project for a IS-ENES Use Case (<http://project-dare.eu/is-enes/>) to develop and deploy a climate service/tool to follow storm tracks (integrated to IS-ENES [climate4impact](#) portal). We have not found any direct usage of CWL for running ESMs.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?

The CWL workflow for tracking storms (DARE H2020 project) is publicly available in gitlab (https://gitlab.com/project-dare/wp7_cyclone-tracking/-/tree/cwl). We have not found any CWL workflows for running ESMs.

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

CWL is an implementation of the Common Workflow Language Standard.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

There is no graphical user interface to compose workflows. Users are expected to have sufficient python programming expertise for composing CWL workflows from the command line.

Does it support running tasks with containers?

Yes. Within the DARE H2020 project, [the cyclone tracking](#) has been [using container technology](#) to be easily integrated with the C4I platform.

Cylc

Cylc is the most known Workflow management System within the Climate Community. It has been initially developed by the Numerical Weather Prediction Community to fulfill their needs when running operational forecasts.

More information about Cylc can be found at <https://cylc.github.io/documentation/>.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

It is not widely used but it is so far the most used.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?

Cylc has been used for running CESM workflows for CMIP6 (see [CESM workflow for CMIP6 documentation](#)). A github repository <https://github.com/NCAR/CESM-WF> allows to create a Cylc suite from the CESM XML environment to automate CESM run. The scripts are very specific to CESM (would need to be adapted for both NorESM and EC-Earth) and are still not platform independent (many hard-coded parameters for running on NCAR's platforms).

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

No. The concept of Cylc is prior to CWL standard and there is no attempt yet to be CWL compliant. The main goal of Cylc is to serve the NWP community and to some extent the climate community.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

There is no graphical interface to compose workflows but there is a graphical interface to monitor running tasks and to visualize the workflow (once created from the command line).

Does it support running tasks with containers?

There is no explicit mention of containers in the documentation but Cylc is versatile enough to be able to accommodate containers for running tasks.

EcFlow

ecFlow is a client/server workflow package that enables users to run a large number of programs (with dependencies on each other and on time) in a controlled environment. It is used at ECMWF to run all the operational suites across a range of platforms. Some meteorological services use ecFlow or similar tools. It is mainly dedicated to operational forecasting and it is very similar to Cylc.

More information can be found at

<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/ECFLOW/ecflow+home>.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

No. Even though ecFlow is very similar to cylc, it has not been widely used or envisaged by the climate community.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMS?

There are examples from the [ecFlow tutorial](#).

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

There is nothing mentioned about interoperability with existing standards.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

As for cylc, there is a graphical interface to visualize the resulting workflow and to monitor running tasks. However, there is no GUI to compose ecFlow workflows.

Does it support running tasks with containers?

Same as for Cylc. There is no explicit mention of containers in the ecFlow documentation but it should not be a problem to run tasks in containers.

Autosubmit

Autosubmit is a python-based workflow manager to create, manage and monitor experiments by using Computing Clusters, HPC's and Supercomputers remotely via ssh. It has support for experiments running in more than one HPC and for different workflow configurations. Autosubmit is Open Source (GNU GPL3 license) and is currently developed and maintained by BSC. It is available from gitlab: <https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/es/autosubmit>.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

It is used at Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) to run models (EC-Earth, MONARCH, NEMO, CALIOPE, HERMES...), operational toolchains (S2S4E), data-download workflows (ECMWF MARS), and many others. It has been tried in the Nordics (at least in Norway) but we have not found extensive usage from the climate community.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?

There is a tutorial (<https://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/en/master/tutorial.html>) but we did not find a registry or shared autosubmit workflows for running EC-Earth or any other ESMs.

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

As most workflow management systems developed by the numerical weather prediction and/or climate community, there is no attempt to follow the Common Workflow Language standard.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

There is no graphical user interface to compose workflows but as for Cylc and ecFlow, there is graphical user interface to monitor experiments (see <https://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/en/master/autosubmit-gui.html> for an example).

Does it support running tasks with containers?

There is no clear mention of containers.

Galaxy

Galaxy (<https://galaxyproject.org/>) is an open, web-based and/or command line platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational research. Galaxy can be accessed on a [free public server](#), or installed locally. Galaxy workflow Management System is inherent to Galaxy but it uses a data centred approach, effectively building a workflow implicitly by applying a series of operations on the data items, keeping a “history” of all intermediate data items that are produced (and how they were made), making it easy to rerun parts of the workflow and share the results with others. Adding a new tool to Galaxy (if it is not already in the [Galaxy Toolshed](#)) is done by making a little Python wrapper and a description.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

Galaxy is not widely used by the climate community. As part of [EOSC-Nordic](#) and other EOSC-related projects (such as [RELIANCE](#)), tools for running and analysing Earth System Models have been integrated (for instance CESM).

There is an interest for using Galaxy for running Earth System Model expressed by the biodiversity community (for instance field ecologists): their background is usually biology and they have often already been “exposed” to Galaxy during their studies and heard about it in international conferences.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?

There are very few examples available yet. Workflowhub (<https://workflowhub.eu/>) contains one or two workflows for running FATES/CLM and CESM (for example <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/65>). However, workflowhub can accommodate workflows from any workflow management system and is therefore not limited to Galaxy.

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

Galaxy is working on Common Workflow Language support.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

Galaxy is the only workflow management system we found with the graphical user interface to compose workflows. There is a very basic GUI for monitoring workflows (while running).

Does it support running tasks with containers?

Galaxy does support containers (docker, singularity).

Snakemake

Snakemake is another workflow management system to create reproducible and scalable data analyses.

Snakemake is very likely the most popular workflow management system, principally due to its simplicity and the fact that workflows are described via a human readable, Python based language.

Is it currently widely used by the Climate community?

We have not found usage of snakemake within the Climate community; at least not for running Earth System Models.

Snakemake is taught as part of [CodeRefinery](#) workshops that are very popular within the Nordic climate community.

Are there any workflows available/shared for running and analysing ESMs?

We did not find any examples related to ESMs.

Is it attempting to be interoperable with existing standards such as the Common Workflow Language Standard?

Yes. From Snakemake 4.8.0, it is possible to refer to CWL tool definitions in rules instead of specifying a wrapper or a plain shell command.

Is there a graphical user interface to compose workflows?

No. There is no graphical interface to compose snakemake workflows (knowledge of python programming is necessary). There is a GUI to visualize finalized snakemake workflows.

Does it support running tasks with containers?

Yes. Snakemake supports running tasks in containers (docker, singularity).